

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

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About this document

Based on the evaluation of high-resolution simulations and its comparison with observations and with results from coarser models, parametrizations of boundary-layer depth, convective mixing and surface fluxes will be assessed, providing recommendations for improved formulations to be tested during the application phase.

Work package in charge:

WP6

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1 Executive summary

Storm-resolving models provide unprecedented realism and new opportunities for comparison to observations, but some processes remain unresolved or partially resolved and need parameterization. This is the case for boundary-layer processes. We focus on the tropical marine boundary layer because of its relevance in cloud radiative feedbacks and validate model data with measurements from the EUREC⁴A field campaign. The simultaneous consideration of ICON and IFS allows us to compare two different strategies. The former simplifies parameterizations to better understand process interactions, sacrificing degrees of freedom to tune the model. The latter considers more sophisticated parameterizations, which allow for better tuning. The results of this study show the value of both. The Smagorinsky model in ICON, despite the simplicity and arguably inappropriate range of application in the kilometer scale, provides boundary-layer properties that are comparable to IFS, which includes a shallow convection scheme, a mass-flux component, and a longer tuning experience. IFS tends to provide better cloud-layer properties, but it depends on the choices of the convective parameterization. Stability correction functions and surface parameterizations can be improved in both models. Both IFS and ICON show greater sensitivity to parameterizations than to grid spacing, which is promising towards certain grid independence in SRMs.

2 Conclusion & Results

The spatio-temporal numerical representation of boundary-layer properties in nextGEMS simulations was validated against measurements during the EUREC⁴A field campaign, which includes data from the Barbados Cloud Observatory (BCO). This campaign took place east of the Barbados island, a region that is representative of the trade-cumulus convection regime. This regime is one of the key elements in the climate system because of its role in Earth's radiative balance, and it is therefore pertinent to ascertain how well the new storm-resolving models (SRMs) represent the atmosphere in this region, particularly the planetary boundary layer where shallow clouds are rooted. For this aim, surface heat and momentum fluxes, boundary-layer profiles, and near-surface properties were analyzed. The comparison during the first phase has focused on data from the BCO, and we have started the comparison with data from the ocean region.

The first main result is that both ICON and IFS models represent well the profiles of wind velocity, temperature, moisture, and liquid-water content observed at the BCO. This includes the various horizontal resolutions and turbulence models considered in the numerical experiments. It is particularly remarkable that ICON with the Smagorinsky model provides such a good estimate without tuning and using coefficients from large-eddy simulations.

We also find some discrepancies between the model representation and the observations. The simulations represented a colder vertical profile than the observations, consistent with global values reported in other projects. The magnitude of the horizontal wind also evolved differently in both models compared to observations, with accumulated biases of about 2–3 m s⁻¹ after 4 weeks. The ICON represented a drier cloud layer between 1–2 km and a moister layer above

it, which is attributed to too much vertical mixing across the top of the cloud layer and suggests some revision of the stability correction function. The IFS model represented this region better than ICON in cycle 2, which was expected because IFS uses a shallow convection scheme, which allows better control of this region. However, the IFS model simulations in cycle 3 were drier close to the surface and moister between 2 and 3 km, compared to cycle 2 simulations, deviating more from the measurements. This was caused by a change in the convection scheme. This sensitivity of results to the boundary-layer parameterization was also observed in ICON, where the change in the turbulence closure model from Smagorinsky to Total Turbulent Energy led to stronger winds, which affected the surface fluxes and vertical profile. On the other hand, both models showed a smaller sensitivity to changes in the grid spacing between 10 and 5 km. This constitutes a second main conclusion, namely, that changes in model physics in this range of kilometer-scale resolution are more important than changes in the horizontal grid spacing. This suggests some degree of grid convergence in some properties.

One question that needs to be further studied is the representation of the near-surface properties, and in particular, the diurnal cycle. Compared to BCO observations, simulations show a diurnal cycle of 2-m air temperature over land that is too strong. If simulation data was sampled over the ocean upstream of the BCO, the agreement with observations improves, which suggests that the surface parameterization in the models is too local, whereas, in reality, horizontal advection seems to play a more important role. How to improve surface parameterizations (Monin-Obukhov similarity theory) seems to remain a challenge in these SRMs, at least in regions of high heterogeneity like islands.

3 Project objectives

The following table lists the overall objectives of nextGEMS. Objectives that the current report contributes to are flagged with yes.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	yes
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	yes
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and	yes
(ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction.	yes

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package:

Objectives of WP6	Relevance in this deliverable?
To identify and evaluate key ocean and marine atmosphere features in the SR-ESM simulations of all three development cycles. (O1)	no
To validate the marine planetary boundary layer representation of the SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	yes
To provide ocean initial conditions for the coupled SR-ESM simulations. (O1)	no
To provide developments towards an ocean mixed layer scheme adequate for SR-ESMs. (O1)	no
To create numerical tools that generate output streams useful to the planetary boundary layer, ocean mixed-layer and fisheries communities. (O1,O3)	no

4 Detailed report on the deliverable

4.1 Material and Methods

This project evaluates the representation of boundary-layer properties in nextGEMS simulations in the tropical oceans. In particular, the study focuses on the tropical Atlantic region where the EUREC⁴A field campaign took place, which allowed us to validate simulations against measurements. This campaign includes measurements at the Barbados Cloud Observatory (BCO), located on the east coast of the island of Barbados, where it is directly exposed to the nearly undisturbed easterly trade wind conditions. The simulations considered the ICON and IFS models performing numerical experiments with distinct grid spacings and parameterization schemes. The evaluation considered surface heat and momentum fluxes, boundary-layer profiles, and near-surface properties. Further details about the simulations and measurements are provided below.

4.1.1 Simulation results

The numerical results come from the nextGEMS simulations, developed under Cycles 1 to 3 with two global storm-resolving models (SRMs) (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/simulations/>). The simulations are performed with the ICOSahedral Nonhydrostatic (ICON) model configured as the ICON-Sapphire (Hohenegger et al., 2023), developed at the Max Planck Institute for Meteorology, and Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) model of the European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF).

The nextGEMS simulations were initialized on 20 January 2020 to align with the EUREC⁴A field campaign, in the same way as the winter DYnamics of the Atmospheric general circulation Modeled On Non-hydrostatic Domains (DYAMOND) intercomparison study (Duras et al., 2021; Hohenegger et al., 2023).

Each model used a different configuration and performed simulations with distinct horizontal resolutions. The main characteristics of the nextGEMS simulations related to the present work are described in Table 3, based on <https://easy.gems.dkrz.de/simulations/>.

Although SRMs simulate at higher grid resolution than conventional general circulation models, some physical processes must be parameterized (Sato et al., 2019). This is the case for boundary-layer processes, radiation, microphysics, and convection. The ICON sapphire configuration does not consider the latter (Hohenegger et al., 2023). Turbulence is handled by the Smagorinsky (Smagorinsky, 1963; Siebesma et al., 2007) scheme in the ICON model (Lee et al., 2022) and by the Eddy-Diffusivity Mass-Flux (EDMF) scheme in the IFS model (Angevine, 2005; Siebesma et al., 2007). Under the second nextGEMS development cycle, an ICON model simulation with 10 km horizontal resolution was performed using the Total Turbulence Energy scheme (Mauritsen et al., 2007) in place of the Smagorinsky scheme, producing the ngc2013 experiment (Table 3).

Despite IFS configuration employing shallow cumulus parameterization for all simulations, the

use of the deep convection scheme differed among the simulations (Table 3). In the IFS cycle 2 simulations, deep convection was turned on in the 9 km resolution experiment called tco1279-orca025, while it was turned off in the 4 km resolution experiment. In cycle 3, there was a change in the use of the deep convection scheme for the IFS model in the experiment with a 4 km resolution. Instead of completely switching the deep convection scheme off, its activity was strongly reduced (Table 3). For this, the cloud base mass flux was reduced by a factor of 5 compared to the default value. This resulted in a realistic probability density function (PDF) of intense precipitation (<https://easy.gems.dkrz.de>).

The model results are saved with distinct time frequencies and, in the case of IFS, with fewer vertical levels than those used during the simulations, as described in Table 4. Although IFS simulations are performed with 137 vertical levels (Table 3), only 23 levels are saved as the output (Table 4). Considering the 137 vertical levels in the IFS, there are 31 levels below 3 km.

Table 3: Characteristics of the nextGEMS simulations. The columns show (from left to right) the nextGEMS development cycle, simulation, atmospheric model, approximate horizontal grid spacing (Δx), number of vertical levels, number of vertical levels below 3 km height, turbulence model, deep convection, and shallow convection schemes.

Cycle	Simulation	Model	Δx	#lev	#lev <3 km	Turbulence scheme	Deep convec.	Shallow convec.
1	dpp0066	ICON	5 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
2	ngc2009	ICON	5 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
2	ngc2012	ICON	10 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
2	ngc2013	ICON	10 km	91	18	Total turbulent energy	off	off
3	ngc3028	ICON	5 km	91	18	Smagorinsky	off	off
2	tco2559- ng5	IFS	4 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	off	on
2	tco1279- orca025	IFS	9 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on	on
3	IFS4- FESOM5	IFS	4 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on "1/5"	on
3	IFS9- NEMO25	IFS	9 km	137	31	K theory and EDMF*	on	on

*Eddy-Diffusivity Mass-Flux

Simulation results from a model grid point were taken to compare with the observations at the BCO. For a proper comparison, the grid point should be chosen to be close to the observation site, and the surface properties should be similar, avoiding representativeness errors (Jiménez and Dudhia, 2012). Despite being located on land, BCO is located adjacent to the ocean and directly exposed to the nearly undisturbed Atlantic trade winds. Then, the closest model grid

Table 4: Characteristics of the nextGEMS simulations output. The columns show (from left to right) the nextGEMS development cycle, simulation, atmospheric model, output type, number of vertical levels, number of vertical levels below 3 km height, and output frequency of the two-dimensional (2D) and three-dimensional (3D) data.

Cycle	Simulation	Model	Output type	# _{lev}	# _{lev} <3 km	Frequency output
1	dpp0066	ICON	native	91	18	2D data: 30m 3D data: 6h
2	ngc2009	ICON	native	91	18	2D data: 30m 3D data: 6h
2	ngc2012	ICON	native	91	18	2D data: 3h 3D data: 23h
2	ngc2013	ICON	native	91	18	2D data: 3h 3D data: 23h
3	ngc3028	ICON	HEALPix grid (zoom = 10)	91	18	2D data: 30m 3D data: 6h
2	tco2559-ng5	IFS	native	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 6h
2	tco1279-orca025	IFS	native	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 6h
3	IFS4-FESOM5	IFS	native	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 6h
3	IFS9-NEMO25	IFS	native	23	10	2D data: 1h 3D data: 6h

points to the BCO, one over land and another over the ocean, were considered for each performed simulation. In this way, it was possible to investigate how the models represented the atmospheric variables at the coastal interface. Fig. 1 shows, as an example, how the ICON simulation with a 5 km horizontal resolution represents surface properties (surface elevation and the land-sea mask), with the selected grid points closest to the BCO to be analyzed.

4.1.2 Measurements

The observational data used in this study was measured during the EUREC⁴A (Elucidating the Role of Clouds Circulation Coupling in Climate) field campaign (Bony et al., 2017; Stevens et al., 2021), which took place in the Atlantic trade-winds region east of Barbados during January and February 2020. This campaign includes island-based measurements at the BCO, which has hosted several common meteorological and advanced active and passive remote sensing instruments since 2010 (Stevens et al., 2016). The BCO is located on the island's upwind (eastern) shore at Deebles Point (13.16°N, 59.43°W). It samples nearly undisturbed Atlantic Ocean trade-wind conditions from the Tradewind Alley, which is an extended corridor where the BCO

Figure 1: Surface elevation (left) and land-sea mask (right) represented in the native grid by the ICON simulation with 5 km horizontal resolution. Each colored hexagon shows the model representation at that grid point.

defines its downwind termination (Stevens et al., 2021).

In the present work, the surface weather station data (Stevens et al., 2016) and the radiosondes launched at the BCO (Stephan et al., 2021) were used. The surface weather station measures humidity, barometric pressure, temperature, precipitation, and wind speed and direction from a mast at a height of 5 m, at a time-frequency of 10 s (Stevens et al., 2016). The radiosondes were launched every four hours, and since there is considerable horizontal drift between the descent and ascent (Albright et al., 2021), only the ascending radiosondes were considered in the present study.

Considering the one-day spin-up time after the start of the nextGEMS simulations as the starting date (21 January 2020) for the analysis period, there are 165 vertical profiles from the radiosondes launched at BCO, with the last one launched on 17 February 2020. To facilitate scientific analyses, Level 2 radiosonde data are provided on a common altitude grid with 10-m vertical resolution (Stephan et al., 2021).

4.2 Results

The results were composed considering the period in which there were simultaneous simulation results and observational data, which was from 21 January to 17 February 2020. As the presence of the surface directly influences the planetary boundary layer and responds to surface forcings, we start by comparing how the different simulations represented the surface fluxes and near-surface variables (Sections 4.2.1 and 4.2.2). The last subsection describes the vertical structure and variability of the boundary layer (Section 4.2.3).

Figure 2: Time-mean field of (top to bottom) surface latent heat flux, surface sensible heat flux, and surface momentum flux for the ICON model simulations in the EUREC⁴A region and period.

4.2.1 Surface and atmospheric near-surface variability in the EUREC⁴A region

The different model configurations impacted the representation of the surface fluxes and near-surface atmospheric variables. For the EUREC⁴A region, negative values of surface sensible and latent heat fluxes were observed (Figs. 2 and 3), which indicates upward fluxes from the ocean to the atmosphere. One main conclusion that can be drawn from those two figures is that ICON and IFS models similarly represent the surface fluxes across different horizontal resolutions and different subgrid-scale parameterizations. The simulation that stood out the most was the ICON-10km-TTE simulation, which uses a total turbulent energy (TTE) scheme (Fig. 2). In this simulation, the surface momentum and latent heat fluxes were represented with higher absolute values, while smaller absolute values in the surface sensible heat flux. As we will show below, this is due to the different representation of near-surface properties when using the TTE scheme. The reason is that the surface layer parameterization used to represent the turbulent surface fluxes makes use of bulk-transfer relationships, in which the fluxes are proportional to the wind speed and the difference of the property between the surface and the near-surface atmosphere (Stull, 2017). The ICON model results in cycle three also call attention to representing high absolute values of the surface fluxes (Fig. 2).

The 10-m winds are shown in Fig. 4 and Fig. 5. All simulations represented the easterly trade-wind conditions, but the wind magnitude changed among them. The 10-m winds in ICON simulations became, on average, 9.5% stronger with the increase of horizontal resolution and 30% stronger, changing the turbulence closure model from Smagorinsky to TTE (Fig. 4 and 5). Although this result was valid over the ocean, which composes most of the analyzed region, the winds became weaker over Barbados and its coastal region when the horizontal resolution increased. The change in horizontal resolution led to minor changes in the IFS winds, with around 5% weaker winds with increased horizontal resolution considering cycles 2 and 3 simulations

Figure 3: Time-mean field of (top to bottom) surface latent heat flux, surface sensible heat flux, and surface momentum flux for the IFS model simulations in the EUREC⁴A region and period.

(Fig. 5 and 5). Comparing all the simulations, the ICON-10km-TTE stands out with a stronger 10-m wind speed (Fig. 4 and Table 5).

Figure 4: Time-mean field of (top to bottom) mean sea level pressure and wind speed for the ICON model simulations in the EUREC⁴A region and period.

This particular behavior of the TTE scheme brings us back to the previous discussion on the representation of the surface fluxes. The wind shear is responsible for turbulent vertical mixing between the boundary layer and the free troposphere, and the wind is responsible for transferring heat, momentum, and mass through the air-sea interface. This explains that the surface fluxes of latent heat and momentum (e.g., Fig. 2) vary proportionally to the wind magnitude (e.g., Fig. 4). This is particularly evident in the simulation with the TTE scheme. The TTE scheme represents a stronger vertical mixing (Lee et al., 2022), which means that more momentum from

Figure 5: Time-mean field of (top to bottom) mean sea level pressure and wind speed for the IFS model simulations in the EUREC⁴A region and period.

the free troposphere is brought downwards towards the surface, which increases the 10-m wind speed. This interpretation is consistent with the vertical profiles we further discuss (Sec. 4.2.3).

However, the surface sensible heat flux did not follow this behavior in the ICON-10km-TTE simulation. The reason is that, besides the wind, another contributing factor is the difference between the surface temperature and the near-surface atmosphere (Figs. 6 and 7). We observe that the ICON-10km-TTE simulation stands out again because, although the surface temperature in this experiment is similar to the other, the 2-m temperature is around 0.5 °C higher on average than the other ICON Cycle 2 simulations (Table 5). The ICON-10km-TTE stronger winds (Fig. 4) favor greater surface fluxes and the warming of the near-surface atmosphere, reducing the surface-air temperature difference and producing small absolute sensible heat flux values. The warming of the near-surface atmosphere is produced through vertical turbulent mixing due to compression as the air descends into higher pressure. On the other way, ICON-10km-Smagorinsky represented weaker 10-m winds (Fig. 4), which induce weaker turbulent mixing in the surface layer, but the higher values of sensible heat flux (excluding cycle 1 data) (Fig. 2) can be explained by the higher surface-air temperature difference (Fig. 6).

Figure 6: Time-mean field of (top to bottom) surface temperature, and 2-m air temperature for the ICON model simulations in the EUREC⁴A region and period.

Figure 7: Time-mean field of (top to bottom) surface temperature, and 2-m air temperature for the IFS model simulations in the EUREC⁴A region and period.

For ICON and IFS models, the higher resolution configuration represented a lower mean surface temperature and a higher mean sea level pressure compared to the lower resolution configuration (Figs. 6, 7, 4, 5). IFS-4km-ngc3 was an exception for the mean sea level pressure since it is lower than IFS-9km-ngc3 (Fig. 5). Comparing the models, ICON simulations represented a higher mean sea level pressure than IFS. Comparing ICON simulations, the mean sea level pressure was 0.5 hPa lower in ICON-10km-TTE compared to ICON-5km. In ICON, the decrease in mean sea level pressure can be related to the expansion of the air due to the warmer surface temperature.

4.2.2 Surface and atmospheric near-surface variability at BCO

As presented in the previous section, the surface and near-surface simulated properties were initially analyzed considering the whole EUREC⁴A region. Here, these simulated properties were analyzed and validated against measurements from the BCO (Fig. 8). The simulation results were taken from one model grid point over the land and another over the ocean, as explained in Section 4.1.1. In this way, it is possible to investigate how the models represent the land-sea interface.

We start describing how the BCO near-surface data changed over time. A diurnal cycle (24 h) is evident for 2-m temperature, while a semi-diurnal cycle (12 h) can be seen for surface pressure. Both cycles are typical in the tropical region for these variables (e.g., Christophersen et al., 2020). The 10-m wind speed presented intra-hour sharper and faster changes, beyond variations along the days.

For surface pressure, all the simulations represented the semi-diurnal variability, although there are discrepancies in the magnitude of the mean pressure. The simulated pressure over sea was closer to the measurements than the simulations over land, and it is related to the fact the pressure decreases with height, and models represent the land grid point with higher topography than reality. It was more challenging to evaluate the time-variability of the wind since it changed

Table 5: Time-space average of the variables in the EUREC⁴A region and period for (top to bottom) surface latent heat flux, surface sensible heat flux, surface temperature, 2-m air temperature, air-surface temperature difference, mean sea level pressure, 10-m wind speed, and surface momentum flux.

Cycle	1	2	2	2	3	2	2	3	3
Model	ICON	ICON	ICON	ICON	ICON	IFS	IFS	IFS	IFS
Δx	5 km	5 km	10 km	10 km	5 km	9 km	4 km	4 km	9 km
Turb.	Smago.	Smago.	Smago.	TTE	Smago.	EDMF	EDMF	EDMF	EDMF
SLHF /Wm⁻²	-180.2	-175.4	-166.0	-208.6	-203.6	-187.7	-181.0	-162.8	-179.3
SSHf /Wm⁻²	-12.6	-11.6	-12.5	-6.4	-14.3	-11.8	-9.3	-11.6	-13.0
ST /°C	26.2	26.4	26.5	26.5	26.3	26.8	26.4	26.3	26.8
T_{2m} /°C	25.2	25.5	25.4	26.0	25.3	25.7	25.6	25.2	25.6
T_{2m} - ST /°C	-1.0	-0.9	-1.1	-0.5	-1.0	-1.0	-0.8	-1.1	-1.2
MSLP /hPa	1015.7	1016.0	1015.7	1015.6	1016.3	1014.5	1014.9	1013.9	1014.4
 U _{10m} /ms⁻¹	6.8	6.9	6.3	8.2	7.5	7.6	7.3	6.9	7.3
TAU /Nm⁻²	0.086	0.083	0.066	0.101	0.099	0.096	0.092	0.076	0.085

more randomly.

About the 10-m mean wind speed, the simulations represented similar magnitudes to the measurements, although it was around 17% overestimated at sea, averaging all simulations. Over the land, the simulations were slightly underestimated, although ICON 10 km simulations were overestimated. As already discussed in the previous section (4.2.1), ICON-10KM-TTE overestimated the 10-m wind speed, and compared to the measurements at BCO, this simulation overestimated the wind speed by 46%.

The wind direction was also validated. The frequency distribution of the 10-m wind direction and speed was evaluated using wind rose diagrams, but the results are not shown here for conciseness. The measured 10-m wind regime presented an easterly flow throughout almost the entire analysis period (90% of the time) associated with the trade winds, and the simulations represented this characteristic in all the cycles and model configurations.

Figure 8: Time-series at the BCO site, considering the closest model grid point to the station data over land (upper) and over sea (bottom).

The diurnal cycle of the 2-m air temperature was evident in the measurements. The amplitude of this cycle was computed as the difference between the data at 14 p.m. and the data at 5 a.m. local time. The average observational amplitude of the diurnal cycle at the BCO is 1.15 °C. The amplitude of the 2-m air temperature was better represented by the models at the sea grid point than at the land grid point, with an average amplitude of 0.55 °C and 2.89 °C for the simulations, respectively. The BCO is located on the island's upwind (eastern) shore and samples the Atlantic trade winds. During the daytime over land, the 2-m temperature increases in response to the warming of the surface due to the sun's short-wave radiation. However, trade winds transport cooler air over the ocean to the land at this location, making the coastal diurnal cycle of 2-m temperatures over land smaller in the real atmosphere. The validation of the simulations against the BCO data suggests that the surface layer parameterization used in the models is too local. This parameterization is based on the Monin-Obukhov similarity theory, and how to improve these schemes seems to remain a challenge in these SRMs, at least in regions of high heterogeneity like islands.

4.2.3 Low-level vertical structure and variability at BCO

Since the simulation results at ocean grid points were in better agreement with observations (Sec. 4.2.2), the simulation results in this section are all from the grid point over the ocean closest to the BCO site.

The atmospheric vertical profiles of the mean and standard deviation of the variables show the variation of each property with height. According to the observed vertical profiles at the BCO (Fig. 9), the temperature and specific humidity decrease with height, and the relative humidity increases until around 700 m and decreases above it. The virtual potential temperature below 700 m was nearly constant but decreased above it. This lower layer corresponds to the sub-cloud layer. On top of it, we can identify a cloud layer up to approximately 2 kilometers, and then the trade inversion where the moisture decreases more rapidly. Wind magnitude decreases towards zero near the ground. The wind speed was nearly constant between the surface layer and 1000 m and decreased above it.

For the simulations, the analysis starts with the most recent results coming from the cycle three simulations. Generally, the profiles at the ocean grid point closest to the BCO are similar among the simulations, representing the main observed characteristics (Fig. 9). It is particularly impressive that ICON can produce such an adequate representation using the Smagorinsky model without any adjustment and by using large-eddy simulation coefficients.

However, we also noted discrepancies between measurements and the simulation results. The simulations represented a colder (around 1 K) vertical profile than the observations, consistent with global values reported in other projects. To better understand this discrepancy, we analyzed separately four periods, the first one considering only the first week of the analysis period, the second one considering the first two weeks, and so on. The results considering different periods are not shown here for conciseness. We observed that the difference between the simulations and the observation temperature is present already in the first week, which suggests that it is present in the initial condition.

Figure 9: Vertical profiles of (left to right) temperature, virtual potential temperature, specific humidity, relative humidity, and horizontal wind speed for the nextGEMS cycle 3 simulations at the highest horizontal resolution. The simulated profiles were taken over the sea from the closest model grid point to the BCO site. The solid line shows the average, and the shading shows the standard deviation. Observations are shown in gray, and simulation results are shown in red.

Between around 1–2 km, ICON represented a drier cloud layer and a moister layer above it, which is related to stronger turbulent vertical mixing across the top of the cloud layer (Fig. 9). The IFS results did not show the drier cloud layer discrepancy, and it might be related to the use of convective parameterizations and the mass-flux part in the boundary layer scheme, while the ICON-Sapphire configuration did not use them (Fig. 9). These parameterizations favor the transport of water vapor upwards into the cloud layer. However, IFS represented slightly drier the lowest 500 m and moister the layers above 2 km than the observations (Fig. 9). These moister layers above 2 km are slightly better represented when the analyzed period is reduced from four weeks to two weeks.

In the cycle 3 simulations, the ICON model represented the wind speed profile in better agreement with the observation than the IFS model (Fig. 9). However, the results change when considering the different time windows, especially for the IFS model. The winds intensified along the EUREC⁴A campaign (Savazzi et al., 2022), so stronger observed wind profiles were verified when considering a longer period. While the ICON model wind profiles consistently followed this behavior, the wind profiles were more steady for the IFS model results.

Comparing the IFS results across the simulation cycles, higher resolution cycle three profiles are colder and moister above ~1.5 km, and the wind speed is weaker, deviating more from the measurements than cycle 2 (Fig. 10). To better understand this, IFS simulations with 9 km resolution from cycles 2 and 3 were compared since the deep convection parameterization was used in both those IFS simulations. On the other side, the use of this parameterization differed between the cycles for the 4 km simulations. Comparing the IFS simulations with 9 km

Figure 10: Vertical profiles of (top to bottom) virtual potential temperature, specific humidity, relative humidity, and horizontal wind speed for the IFS simulations. The simulated profiles were taken over the sea from the closest model grid point to the BCO site. The solid line shows the average, and the shading shows the standard deviation. Observations are shown in gray, and simulation results are shown in red.

resolution, it was possible to determine that there was no change in potential temperature, and humidity changed just a bit from cycle 2 to cycle 3. Then, the source for the differences in the IFS 4 km cycles 2 and 3 can be explained to mostly come from using the deep convection scheme in cycle 3. It should be highlighted that the deep convection parameterization was on in cycle 3 only with 1/5 of cloud-base mass flux.

This sensitivity of results to using different parameterizations was also observed in ICON (Fig 11) and affected the vertical profiles. The change in the turbulence closure model from Smagorinsky to TTE led to stronger winds, which are associated with turbulent vertical mixing. In the ICON-

Figure 11: Vertical profiles of (top to bottom) virtual potential temperature, specific humidity, relative humidity, and horizontal wind speed for the ICON simulations. The simulated profiles were taken over the sea from the closest model grid point to the BCO site. The solid line shows the average, and the shading shows the standard deviation. Observations are shown in gray, and simulation results are shown in red.

10km-TTE simulation, stronger turbulent vertical mixing transports momentum downward from the free troposphere and enhances the winds in the boundary layer. This turbulent vertical mixing is also responsible for warming up the boundary layer, as can be seen from the profiles, but also in the 2-m temperature from Section (4.2.1). Although ICON-10km-TTE represented a warmer vertical profile in better agreement with measurements, it could result from a discrepancy in the representation of some processes. Such processes could be a stronger vertical mixing and the representation of fewer clouds, which would permit more short-wave radiation from the sun to reach the surface and heat it up. ICON and IFS models showed a smaller sensitivity to changes

in the grid spacing between 10 and 5 km compared to model physics. This suggests some degree of grid convergence in some properties.

The boundary-layer depth was estimated using the bulk Richardson number, which considers the ratio of the turbulence related to buoyancy to that associated with mechanical shear effects (e.g., Lavers et al., 2019). The boundary-layer depth and the atmospheric variables analyzed in this section were also investigated using time-height section diagrams. We do not show the results here, for conciseness, but both approaches provided boundary-layer properties that were consistent with the BCO profiles shown before.

5 References (Bibliography)

- Albright, A. L., B. Fildier, L. Touzé-Peiffer, R. Pincus, J. Vial, and C. Muller (2021). “Atmospheric radiative profiles during EUREC⁴A”. In: *Earth System Science Data* 13.2, pp. 617–630. DOI: [10.5194/essd-13-617-2021](https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-617-2021).
- Angevine, W. M. (2005). “An Integrated Turbulence Scheme for Boundary Layers with Shallow Cumulus Applied to Pollutant Transport”. In: *Journal of Applied Meteorology* 44.9, pp. 1436–1452. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAM2284.1>.
- Bony, S., B. Stevens, F. Ament, S. Bigorre, P. Chazette, S. Crewell, J. Delanoë, K. Emanuel, D. Farrell, C. Flamant, et al. (2017). “EUREC⁴A: A field campaign to elucidate the couplings between clouds, convection and circulation”. In: *Surveys in Geophysics* 38, pp. 1529–1568. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10712-017-9428-0>.
- Christoffersen, J. A., G. R. Foltz, and R. C. Perez (2020). “Surface Expressions of Atmospheric Thermal Tides in the Tropical Atlantic and Their Impact on Open-Ocean Precipitation”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 125.22. e2019JD031997 2019JD031997, e2019JD031997. DOI: [10.1029/2019JD031997](https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD031997).
- Duras, J., F. Ziemann, and D. Klocke (2021). “The DYAMOND Winter data collection”. In: DOI: [10.5194/egusphere-egu21-4687](https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-egu21-4687).
- Hohenegger, C., P. Korn, L. Linardakis, R. Redler, R. Schnur, P. Adamidis, J. Bao, S. Bastin, M. Behraves, M. Bergemann, et al. (2023). “ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales”. In: *Geoscientific Model Development* 16.2, pp. 779–811. DOI: [10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023](https://doi.org/10.5194/gmd-16-779-2023).
- Jiménez, P. A. and J. Dudhia (2012). “Improving the Representation of Resolved and Unresolved Topographic Effects on Surface Wind in the WRF Model”. In: *Journal of Applied Meteorology and Climatology* 51.2, pp. 300–316. DOI: [10.1175/JAMC-D-11-084.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/JAMC-D-11-084.1).
- Lavers, D. A., A. Beljaars, D. S. Richardson, M. J. Rodwell, and F. Pappenberger (2019). “A Forecast Evaluation of Planetary Boundary Layer Height Over the Ocean”. In: *Journal of Geophysical Research: Atmospheres* 124.9, pp. 4975–4984. DOI: [10.1029/2019JD030454](https://doi.org/10.1029/2019JD030454).
- Lee, J., C. Hohenegger, A. Chlond, and R. Schnur (2022). “The Climatic Role of Interactive Leaf Phenology in the Vegetation- Atmosphere System of Radiative-Convective Equilibrium Storm-Resolving Simulations”. In: *Tellus B: Chemical and Physical Meteorology* 74.1, p. 164. ISSN: 0280-6509. DOI: [10.16993/tellusb.26](https://doi.org/10.16993/tellusb.26).
- Mauritsen, T., G. Svensson, S. S. Zilitinkevich, I. Esau, L. Enger, and B. Grisogono (2007). “A Total Turbulent Energy Closure Model for Neutrally and Stably Stratified Atmospheric Boundary Layers”. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 64.11, pp. 4113–4126. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/2007JAS2294.1>.
- Satoh, M., B. Stevens, F. Judt, M. Khairoutdinov, S.-J. Lin, W. M. Putman, and P. Düben (2019). “Global Cloud-Resolving Models”. In: *Current Climate Change Reports* 5.3, pp. 172–184. ISSN: 2198-6061. DOI: [10.1007/s40641-019-00131-0](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40641-019-00131-0).
- Savazzi, A. C. M., L. Nuijens, I. Sandu, G. George, and P. Bechtold (2022). “The representation of the trade winds in ECMWF forecasts and reanalyses during EUREC⁴A”. In: *Atmospheric Chemistry and Physics* 22.19, pp. 13049–13066. DOI: [10.5194/acp-22-13049-2022](https://doi.org/10.5194/acp-22-13049-2022).
- Siebesma, A. P., P. M. M. Soares, and J. Teixeira (2007). “A Combined Eddy-Diffusivity Mass-Flux Approach for the Convective Boundary Layer”. In: *Journal of the Atmospheric Sciences* 64.4, pp. 1230–1248. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1175/JAS3888.1>.

Smagorinsky, J. (1963). “General circulation experiments with the primitive equations: I. The basic experiment.” In: *Monthly Weather Review* 91.3, pp. 99–164. DOI: [https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493\(1963\)091<0099:GCEWTP>2.3.CO;2](https://doi.org/10.1175/1520-0493(1963)091<0099:GCEWTP>2.3.CO;2).

Stephan, C. C., S. Schnitt, H. Schulz, H. Bellenger, S. P. de Szoeke, C. Acquistapace, K. Baier, T. Dauhut, R. Laxenaire, Y. Morfa-Avalos, R. Person, E. Quiñones Meléndez, G. Bagheri, T. Böck, A. Daley, J. Güttler, K. C. Helfer, S. A. Los, A. Neuberger, J. Röttenbacher, A. Raeke, M. Ringel, M. Ritschel, P. Sadoulet, I. Schirmacher, M. K. Stolla, E. Wright, B. Charpentier, A. Doerenbecher, R. Wilson, F. Jansen, S. Kinne, G. Reverdin, S. Speich, S. Bony, and B. Stevens (2021). “Ship- and island-based atmospheric soundings from the 2020 EUREC⁴A field campaign”. In: *Earth System Science Data* 13.2, pp. 491–514. DOI: [10.5194/essd-13-491-2021](https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-491-2021).

Stevens, B., S. Bony, D. Farrell, F. Ament, A. Blyth, C. Fairall, J. Karstensen, P. K. Quinn, S. Speich, C. Acquistapace, et al. (2021). “EUREC⁴A”. In: *Earth System Science Data* 13.8, pp. 4067–4119. DOI: [10.5194/essd-13-4067-2021](https://doi.org/10.5194/essd-13-4067-2021).

Stevens, B., D. Farrell, L. Hirsch, F. Jansen, L. Nuijens, I. Serikov, B. Brüggmann, M. Forde, H. Linne, K. Lonitz, and J. M. Prospero (2016). “The Barbados Cloud Observatory: Anchoring Investigations of Clouds and Circulation on the Edge of the ITCZ”. In: *Bulletin of the American Meteorological Society* 97.5, pp. 787–801. DOI: [10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00247.1](https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-14-00247.1).

Stull, R. (2017). “Practical meteorology”. In: *An Algebra-based Survey of Atmospheric Science*.

6 Dissemination and uptake

6.1 Uptake by the targeted audience

As indicated in the Description of the Action, the audience for this deliverable is:

x	The general public (PU)
	The project partners, including the Commission services (PP)
	A group specified by the consortium, including the Commission services (RE)
	This reports is confidential, only for members of the consortium, including the Commission services (CO)

6.2 This is how we are going to ensure the uptake of the deliverables by the targeted audience

This document will be freely available to the general public from the project website (<https://nextgems-h2020.eu/>).

7 Deliverable timeliness

Is the deliverable delayed?

yes

The delay of this deliverable was discussed with the nextGEMS PO.

8 Changes made and/or difficulties encountered, if any

Not applicable.

9 Sustainability

Links built with other deliverables, WPs, and synergies created with other projects

A link is built with the deliverables D6.1 "Report on the SR-ESMs evaluation," and D4.3 "Report with priority list of sub-grid scale processes to address and improve in phase two", developed by groups we collaborate with.

10 Full track of dissemination activities

- Cycle 1 Hackathon 19. – 22. October 2021 in Berlin
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2022
- Office Hour with IBERDROLA on solar energy in January 2022
- UCM Student Hackathon, 01. – 03. April 2022 near Madrid
- Cycle 2 Hackathon 26. June – 02. July 2022 in Vienna
- Storms & Ocean summer slackathon 31. June – 06. July 2022 at the Bornö Institute for ocean and climate studies, Sweden
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2023
- Mini-hackathon of Storms & Land at Wageningen University 04. – 06. April 2023
- Cycle 3 Hackathon 29. May – 02. June 2023 in Madrid
- "Science meets Art" - NextCalendArt 2024

11 Full track of publications and IP

Publications within the project can be found on our website: <https://nextgems-h2020.eu/publications/>